

Supporting Information

Improving Mass Transport and Charge Transfer in COF-Based Photocatalysts with Three-Dimensional Ordered Macropores for Benzylamine Oxidation and Hydrogen Evolution

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Table of content

S1. Experimental section	3
S1.1 Chemicals and materials	3
S1.2. Preparation of polystyrene spheres (PS) colloid.....	3
S1.3 Preparation of 3D ordered PS template	3
S1.4 Preparation of 3DOM Tp-Tta covalent organic framework (3DOM-COFs)	3
S1.5 Preparation of bulk Tp-Tta covalent organic framework (B-COFs)	4
S1.6. Preparation of ZnCdS (ZCS) nanoparticle	4
S1.7. Preparation of ZCS/3DOM-COF composite samples	4
S1.8. Preparation of ZCS/B-COF composite samples	4
S1.9. Characterization.....	4
S1.10. Photoelectrochemical Measurements	5
S1.11 Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR).....	5
S1.12 Femtosecond transient absorption (fs-TA) test.....	6
S1.13 In situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (In situ DRIFTS) test	6
S1.14 Photocatalytic Measurements of Benzylamine (BA) to N-benzylbenzaldimine (NBI) and H ₂	6
S1.15 Finite Element Method Simulations.....	7
S1.16 Computational details	7
S2. Supporting Figures	9
Morphological and structural analysis.....	9
Photocatalytic activity analysis.....	23
Theoretical calculation	31
Charge separation efficiency analysis	34
Geometry and boundary conditions of mass Transfer behavior	39
Table: Key porosity parameters, Article on activity comparison, Boundary conditions and parameters used in simulations, and fs-TA analysis	41
Reference.....	47

S1. Experimental section

S1.1 Chemicals and materials

1,3,5-triformylphloroglucinol (Tp), 4,4',4''-(1,3,5-triazine-2,4,6-triyl) trianiline (Tta), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP, 30 k) were bought from Aladdin Industrial Corporation (Shanghai, China). Chromium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 99.5\%$), zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 99\%$), sodium sulfide nine water ($\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 99.5\%$), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{OS}$, $\geq 99\%$), potassium persulfate ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, 99 wt.%), styrene (C_8H_8 , 99%), sodium hydroxide pellets (NaOH, 96%) were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. Deionized water (18.2 M Ω , 300.6 K). All chemicals were used as received without further purification

S1.2. Preparation of polystyrene spheres (PS) colloid

Monodisperse colloidal polystyrene spheres (PS: ~ 340 nm) were synthesized as reported.^[1] In a typical procedure, 70 mL of styrene was thoroughly washed with 20 mL of 10 wt.% NaOH solution, followed by deionized water to remove stabilizers. Subsequently, 65 mL of the washed styrene was added to a 1 L round-bottom flask with 500 mL of water containing 2.5 g of PVP. The mixture was bubbled with N_2 for 15 min, and stirred at 60°C in an oil bath for 30 minutes. Then, 50 mL of water containing 1 g of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ was rapidly added to initiate the polymerization. The reaction was stirred with 500 rpm at 60°C for 24 h, followed by cooling to yield a milky product PS colloid.

S1.3 Preparation of 3D ordered PS template

45 mL of PS colloid was sonicated to form a uniform emulsion. This emulsion was then centrifuged 2000 rpm for 12 h. The resulting precipitate was dried overnight at 60°C to obtain the 3D ordered PS template.

S1.4 Preparation of 3DOM Tp-Tta covalent organic framework (3DOM-COFs)

First, 0.13 mmol Tp was dissolved in 5 mL of DMSO solution. 1 g of PS template was then immersed in the solution for 30 min, followed by vacuum degassing for 5 min to allow the precursor solution to uniformly penetrate into the template. After purging with N_2 gas, 1 mL of DMSO solution containing Tta (0.07 mmol) was added. A two-step gradient heating process was conducted, first maintaining mixture at 60°C for 6 h, and then increasing the temperature to 120°C for 72 h. The resulting precipitate was washed twelve times each with methanol, DMF, and THF, then vacuum dried overnight at 70°C.

S1.5 Preparation of bulk Tp-Tta covalent organic framework (B-COFs)

B-COFs sample was prepared with same method without using PS template.

S1.6. Preparation of ZnCdS (ZCS) nanoparticle

1 mmol of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 1 mmol of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were dissolved in 150 mL of deionized water. The solution was stirred vigorously at room temperature for 1 h. Next, 20 mL of deionized water containing 2.5 mmol of $\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added dropwise at 1 mL/min, and stirring continued for 8 h. After 12 h, the precipitate was washed six times with deionized water by centrifugation, followed by drying at 70°C to obtain ZnCdS nanoparticles (ZCS).

S1.7. Preparation of ZCS/3DOM-COF composite samples

A given amount of 3DOM-COF was dispersed in 150 mL of deionized water. Then, 1 mmol of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 1 mmol of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were added and stirred vigorously at room temperature for 1 h. Subsequently, 20 mL of deionized water containing 2.5 mmol of $\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added dropwise at 1 mL/min, and stirring continued for 8 h. After reaction for 12 h, the precipitate was washed several times with deionized water by centrifugation, followed by vacuum drying at 70°C . The resulting samples were labeled based on the mass ration of 3DOM-COFs:ZCS. such as ZCS/3DOM-COFs-15 (15 wt.%), ZCS/3DOM-COFs-20 (20 wt.%), and ZCS/3DOM-COFs-25 (25 wt.%).

S1.8. Preparation of ZCS/B-COF composite samples

ZCS/B-COF materials were prepared with identical method with ZCS/3DOM-COFs without using PS template.

S1.9. Characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements were performed on a SmartLab (Rigaku) diffraction gauge with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation at scanning rate of 2° min^{-1} . A BRUKE Tensor-27 spectrometer was used for obtaining the Fourier transformation infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra were performed on a ESCALAB 250XI (Thermo system). ISI XPS (Thermo ESCALAB 250Xi) was carried out to test the charges transfer pathway on the photocatalyst. The test conditions were monochrome $\text{Al K}\alpha$ ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$) with a power of 150 W and a $400 \mu\text{m}$ beam spot. Finally, the test results were corrected by taking C1s as 284.8 eV . The morphological characteristics of the composite sample were observed by JXA-840A (JEOL) field emission scanning electron microscopy (SEM), (TEM, JEOL JEM-2100) high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM),

along with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) element mapping data. In order to investigate the light absorption ability of the samples, UV-visible diffuse reflectance absorbance tests were performed on the samples. The equipment used was an ultraviolet-visible photometer (UV-2600) from Shimadzu, Japan. The test conditions were: the substrate barium sulfate (BaSO_4), and the test wavelength range was 200 nm - 1400 nm. Photoluminescence (PL) spectra and time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) were recorded on QuamansterTM40 spectrophotometer (Photonics International inc.) with an excitation wavelength of 380 nm. In order to investigate the specific surface area and pore size distribution of the samples, the samples were tested for specific surface area (BET) using a fully automated specific surface and pore size distribution analyzer (Mac 2460). Prior to gas adsorption treatment samples were degassed at 150 °C for 12 h under vacuum. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) from 20-900 °C was carried out on an TG50 analyzer (Mettler-Toledo) under N_2 atmosphere using a 10 °C/min ramp without equilibration delay. A surface photovoltage spectrometer (PL-SPS/IPCE1000) was used to measure the steady-state surface photovoltage (SPV) spectrum.

S1.10. Photoelectrochemical Measurements

Photoelectrochemical measurements were performed using a CHI660E electrochemical analyzer (Shanghai, China) in a standard three-electrode configuration. The prepared samples were deposited onto fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass substrates, which served as the working electrode, while a standard Ag/AgCl electrode and platinum foil were used as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. A 0.5 mol L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 solution was used as the electrolyte. The preparation of the working electrode followed the same procedure as in previous studies. Transient photocurrent responses (*i-t* curves) were recorded under a 3 W LED lamp (365 nm) with periodic ON/OFF illumination cycles, using a 0.6 V bias potential. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted at a frequency range of 0.01– 10^5 Hz with an AC amplitude of 10 mV under open-circuit voltage conditions.

S1.11 Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR)

The free radical signals were recorded using an EPR spectrometer (Bruker A300) with 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide (DMPO) as the trapping agent. For the detection of superoxide radicals ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$), 5 mg of the catalyst was dispersed in a DMPO/methanol solution, and the signals were collected both in the dark and under light irradiation ($\lambda = 420$ nm). For the detection of hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$), 5 mg of the catalyst was dispersed in a DMPO/ H_2O solution, and

the signals were recorded under both dark and light conditions using a 420 nm LED. For detecting amine free radicals, 5 mg of the sample was dispersed in an H₂O/acetonitrile solution, and after purging with Ar for 30 min, 0.1 mL of benzylamine and 100 μL of DMPO were added to the solution. The signals were collected under dark and light irradiation with a 420 nm LED.

S1.12 Femtosecond transient absorption (fs-TA) test

The fs-TA spectra for this study were obtained using a regenerative amplified Ti: sapphire laser system from Coherent (800 nm, 35 fs, 6 mJ pulse⁻¹, 1 kHz repetition rate), nonlinear frequency mixing techniques, and the Femto-TA100 spectrometer (Time-Tech Spectra). The 800 nm output from the regenerative amplifier was split into two parts using a 50% beam splitter. One part was directed to pump a TOPAS Optical Parametric Amplifier (OPA) to generate a wavelength-tunable pump beam (250 nm to 2.5 μm). The reflected 800 nm beam was split again, with less than 10% of the beam attenuated by a neutral density filter and focused into a 2 mm thick sapphire window to generate a white light continuum (340 nm to 600 nm) used for the probe beam. The probe beam was focused onto the sample using an Al parabolic reflector. After passing through the sample, the probe beam was collimated and directed into a fiber-coupled spectrometer with CMOS sensors, detected at a 1 kHz frequency. The pump-probe delay was controlled using a motorized delay stage. The pump pulses were chopped at 500 Hz by a synchronized chopper, and the absorbance change was calculated by comparing two adjacent probe pulses (pump-blocked and pump-unblocked).

S1.13 In situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (In situ DRIFTS) test

The photocatalyst with addition of BA solution was placed in the cuvette and kept under argon atmosphere for 30 min. The infrared spectra were recorded on a diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectrometer (Nicolet iS10 (Thermo)). The infrared spectra were recorded from 0 to 40 min during irradiation with a 420 nm LED lamp (3W).

S1.14 Photocatalytic Measurements of Benzylamine (BA) to N-benzylbenzaldimine (NBI) and H₂

Photocatalytic conversion of BA to NBI and H₂ was performed in a 50 mL quartz reactor. A mixture of 5 mg catalyst, 20 mL H₂O/acetonitrile solution, and 3.5 mmol BA was added to the reactor. The mixture was purged with N₂ for 30 min to remove air before irradiation. The sealed reactor was placed under an 80 W LED light source (λ = 420 nm). After the reaction, H₂ content was measured using a Shimadzu GC-2014 gas chromatograph with a thermal conductivity detector. Liquid products were analyzed using an Agilent A91PLUS gas chromatograph with the following heating program: initial temperature 40°C (hold for 5 min), ramp to 250°C at 20°C/min (hold for 10 min). Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. For

recycling experiments, the reactor was purged with N₂ for 30 min after each cycle. The selectivity of BA to NBI was calculated using the following equations:

$$\text{Selectivity (\%)} = \frac{2C_{NBI}}{C_0 - C_{BA}} \times 100\%$$

Here C₀ is the initial moles of BA; C_{BA} and C_{NBI} are the moles of the residual BA and the corresponding NBI, respectively.

The apparent quantum efficiency (AQE) for H₂ generation is calculated according to the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AQE} &= \frac{2 \times \text{Numbers of evolved H}_2}{\text{Numbers of incident photons}} \times 100\% \\ &= \frac{2 \times M \times N_A \times c \times h}{p \times t \times \lambda} \times 100\% \end{aligned}$$

Where M represents the amount of produced H₂, N_A is Avogadro constant, c is the speed of light, h is the Planck constant, P is the intensity of the irradiation, t is the time of illumination, and λ is the wavelength.

S1.15 Finite Element Method Simulations

For the simulation of mass transfer process, COMSOL Multiphysics was used to build a simplified computational domain according to the experimentally characterized size, structure and morphology of the catalysts. A micrometer magnitude scale was used for the size of both 3DOM-COFs and B-COFs catalysts. Periodic condition was used to describe the upper and bottom boundaries of the computational domain. A fixed concentration C=C₀ (C₀ is BA concentration in bulk solution) was used for the left the right boundaries to describe the contact with bulk solution. With the ordered macropores in 3DOM-COF, it was assumed that the bulk solution filled the macropores during the simulation. The boundary conditions for the interface between macropores and bulk catalyst were set as C=C₀. The detailed physical parameters used in the simulation including the material properties are provided in Table S4.

The model equations governing the mass transfer of BA species are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-D_i \nabla c_i) &= R_i \\ N_i &= -D_i \nabla c_i \end{aligned}$$

where c_i is noted for the concentration of species i (with $i = \text{BA}$), D_i is the diffusion coefficient of species i . R is reaction rate which is set as 0 for purely investigating the mass transfer performance of the species. N_i is the diffusion flux.

S1.16 Computational details

Three different supercells have been created, one for each structure considered in the study. For the COF, a 3.2x1.8 nm supercell was considered. A vacuum space of 2 nm in the z direction (perpendicular to the basal plane) was used in all cells to avoid interactions between

periodic images. Only the part of the COF in proximity with the catalytic center was allowed to optimize, while the rest was kept frozen. Considering the reduced size of the ZCS nanoparticle where the catalysis takes place, we model it as a planar surface with cell dimension of 1.4x1.6 nm, considering the 101 surface. Three layers were considered for the calculations, to model the bulk material, and the first one was allowed to optimize, while the last two were kept frozen. Finally, a 3.0x2.0 nm supercell was built for the heterojunction. This dimension was chosen to decrease as much as possible the cell in commensuration (as COF and CZS have different unit cells). To decrease computational costs, only the first layer of the CZS was treated explicitly, and the same criteria for optimization as introduced for the COF was observed. After optimization of the surfaces, BA was adsorbed on the respective active atoms and optimized. All the subsequent intermediates have been generated from the optimized precursors.

All calculations were performed using spin-polarized density functional theory (DFT) as implemented in the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP).²⁻⁴ The Perdew-Burke-Emzerhof (PBE) functional with a plane-wave cutoff energy of 500 eV was used. For structural optimizations, the Brillouin zone was sampled using a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ k-point grid based on the Monkhorst-Pack scheme, centered at Gamma. The k-points were increase to a 6x6x1 grid for the DOS calculations. The convergence criteria for the force on each atom was set to 0.02 eV/Å, while the electronic structure energy convergence criterion was 10^{-5} eV. The Grimme D3 method with Becke-Johnson parameters⁵ were employed to account for Van der Waals interactions.⁶ All calculations were performed in PCM water solvent. The vibrational modes were calculated at 298.15 K to obtain the zero-point energy, entropy, and temperature corrections to enthalpy. Bader charges were considered for the charge transfer analysis.

S2. Supporting Figures

Morphological and structural analysis

Figure S1. Low magnification SEM image, reveal a uniform large-pore distribution over a $12 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ area.

Figure S2. (a) Average size of monodisperse colloidal PS spheres and (b) graph of monodisperse colloidal PS spheres as a stable dispersion in aqueous solution.

Note: The illustration in Figure S2 depicts the size of spheres in the SEM image, followed by diameter measurement using digital micrograph software, with an error controlled within $d = 340 \pm 10$.

Figure S3. (a, b) Low-magnification SEM images of PS template. High-magnification SEM images of (c) closely spaced PS and (d) parallel aligned PS.

Figure S4. Low magnification TEM image.

Figure S5. TEM images of (a) 3DOM-COF and (b) B-COF.

Figure S6. Simulated packing structures for Tp-Tta COF (O: red; N: blue; C: gray; H: white).

Figure S7. FTIR spectra of B-COF, 3DOM-COF, PS, Tp and Tta.

Note: Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy analysis can be utilized to study molecular structures and chemical bonds, serving as a method for characterization and identification of chemical species. As shown in Figure S7, PS exhibits distinct vibrational modes at $\sim 1490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and in the $600\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, corresponding to aromatic C=C stretching and C-H out-of-plane bending, respectively. In contrast, B-COF and 3DOM-COF do not show these PS-specific features, particularly the C-H bending vibrations in the $600\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. Peaks at 1622 , 1576 , and 1280 cm^{-1} in the B-COF and 3DOM-COF correspond to the asymmetric vibrations of C=N, C=C, and -C-N=C- bonds, respectively. These results confirm that the template is almost completely removed, without altering the COF structure.

Figure S8. XPS spectra of (a) survey, (b) C 1s, (c) N 1s and (d) O 1s of 3DOM-COF.

Note: As shown in Figure S8, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis reveals that 3DOM-COF is primarily composed of C, N, and O elements. The high-resolution C 1s spectrum of 3DOM-COF can be deconvoluted into four peaks. One peak centered at 284.8 eV can be assigned to the C=C benzene ring, peak at 286.5 eV belongs to C-N bonds, peak at 289.1 eV corresponds to C=O bonds, and peak at 287.3 eV is attributed to the C=N triazine ring. In the high-resolution N 1s spectrum, three characteristic peaks are observed at binding energies of 398.7 eV, 400.2 eV, and 403.3 eV, corresponding to heterocycles (C=N-C), triazine (N-(C)₃), and triazine (C=N) π excitation or positive charge localization, respectively. The high-resolution O 1s spectrum exhibits two characteristic peaks at 531.1 eV (C=O) and 533.1 eV (-OH), respectively.

Figure S9. The TGA curve of 3DOM-COF measured up to 900 °C in N₂.

Note: The samples were thermally activated under vacuum and dried at 120 °C for 12 h prior to testing. The TGA curve shows no significant mass loss below 150 °C, indicating the effective removal of physisorbed species. The minor weight loss observed between 150-300 °C is attributed to the decomposition of surface functional groups. The primary decomposition occurring above 300 °C corresponds to the thermal degradation of the COF framework, consistent with previous reports on analogous COFs.⁷

Figure S10. Experimental XRD patterns after 24 h exposure to various solvents over ZCS/3DOM-COF composite.

Note: To rigorously evaluate stability, 3DOM-COF was immersed in 2 M HCl (aq), 0.5 M NaOH (aq), 1,4-dioxane, and acetonitrile for 24 h, followed by XRD analysis. As shown in Figure 10, the characteristic diffraction peaks of 3DOM-COF were well retained after acid treatment, with no shift or distortion in peak position, indicating its excellent stability. After alkaline treatment, the diffraction peaks remained unchanged in position and shape, indicating preserved framework integrity. The slight decrease in intensity may be due to edge-site hydrolysis of β -ketoenamine linkages. Excellent stability was also observed in organic solvents (1,4-dioxane, acetonitrile).

Figure S11. (a) SEM image (b) TEM image and (c) HR-TEM image of ZCS.

Figure S12. XRD patterns of ZCS and ZCS/3DOM-COF composite.

Note: As shown in Figure S12, the XRD measurement results indicate that ZCS exhibits three main peaks located at 27.8° , 46.02° , and 54.58° , corresponding to the (002), (110), and (112) diffraction planes, respectively. In addition, the corresponding peaks of ZCS and 3DOM-COF are shown simultaneously in ZCS/3DOM-COF, confirmed the successful loading of the composite sample.

Figure S13. (a) N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms and (b) pore size distributions of ZCS/3DOM-COF and ZCS/B-COF.

As shown in Figure S13, the observed specific surface area reduction in ZCS/B-COF primarily stems from partial pore occupation within the intrinsic microporous framework of B-COF (pore size ~ 1.4 nm). In the case of ZCS/B-COF, the slight decrease in BET surface area is mainly attributed to the uneven distribution of ZCS nanoparticles, which only partially cover the COF surface and leave most of the pores accessible. In contrast, the more uniform distribution of ZCS nanoparticles within the 3DOM structure leads to a significant decrease in BET surface area ($635.2 \rightarrow 178.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). These results support our design strategy, highlighting that constructing a 3DOM architecture is advantageous for integrating nanoparticles into hybrid materials.

Figure S14. FTIR spectra of ZCS, B-COF, 3DOM-COF, and ZCS/3DOM-COF composite.

Figure S15. (a) UV-Vis spectra of B-COF, 3DOM-COF, ZCS, ZCS/B-COF and ZCS/3DOM-COF. (b) Band gap of B-COF, 3DOM-COF and ZCS samples.

Figure S16. Mott-Schottky plot of the (a) B-COF, (b) 3DOM-COF and (c) ZCS.

Note: As shown in Figure S16, Mott-Schottky (M-S) curves were measured to study the energy level alignment between B-COF, 3DOM-COF, and ZCS. The positive slopes of B-COF, 3DOM-COF and ZCS indicate their n-type properties, and the flat bands are extrapolated to -0.51 , -0.47 and -1.09 V vs normal hydrogen electrode (NHE), respectively.

Figure S17. Energy level structures of 3DOM-COF and ZCS.

Figure S18. XPS spectra of 3DOM-COF, ZCS/3DOM-COF and ZCS samples.

Figure S19. In-situ irradiated XPS spectra of (a) Zn 2p (b) Cd 3d, (c) C 1s and (d) O 1s of ZCS/3DOM-COF composite with/without light irradiation.

Figure S20. Work functions of (a) ZCS and (b) COF.

Photocatalytic activity analysis

Figure S21. The irradiance spectrum of 80 W LED light source with 420 nm filter.

Note: As shown in Figure S21, only the light accumulated at 420 nm can pass through the optical filter and be used for the exciting light for photocatalysis, indicating that ZCS/3DOM-COF is a visible-light photocatalyst.

Figure S22. (a) GC and (b-c) MS spectra of ZCS/3DOM-COF and ZCS.

Figure S23. (a-d) ^{13}C NMR and (e-h) ^1H NMR of the products on 3DOM-COF, ZCS/3DOM-COF-20 and ZCS.

Note: Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra (Figure S23 a-d) and carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR) spectra (Figure S23 e-h) confirm the major products obtained on 3DOM-COF, ZCS/3DOM-COF, and ZCS. No signal of DBA is observed over 3DOM-COF and ZCS/3DOM-COF catalysts. However, for ZCS, the ^{13}C NMR spectrum shows a signal of the carbon atom on the C-N-C moiety of DBA at 49.4 ppm, and the ^1H NMR spectrum shows a signal of the hydrogen atom on the C-N-C moiety of DBA at 5.3 ppm.

Figure S24. (a) H₂ and NBI generation at different times; (b) H₂ and NBI formation rate at different times.

Note: To assess the temporal evolution of the reaction, time-dependent experiments were performed at 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 h. The H₂ evolution rate and BA oxidation efficiency exhibit a nearly linear correlation with time (**Figure S24a**), with an average H₂ evolution rate of ~17.8 mmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹ and an NBI formation rate of 15.1 mmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (**Figure S24b**). This indicates that the catalyst is capable of sustaining stable and efficient conversions.

Figure S25. Comparison of H₂ evolution and NBI production rates under LED $\lambda = 420$ nm illumination over different samples.

Figure S26. AQE of the ZCS/3DOM-COF.

Figure S27. H₂ and NBI generation rates of ZCS/3DOM-COF for five successive cycles.

Note: The photocatalytic activity remains high even after five cycles (with H₂ activity retention of approximately 80% and NBI activity retention of approximately 86%), indicating that the material exhibits reasonable cyclic stability. This slight decrease in activity could be attributed to the partial adsorption of reactive intermediates on the COF surface, temporarily blocking active sites.

Figure S28. XRD patterns for ZCS/3DOM-COF before (red line) and after (black line) the 3 h irradiation reaction.

Figure S29. TEM image for ZCS/3DOM-COF after the 3 h irradiation reaction.

Figure S30. H₂ and NBI generation of ZCS/3DOM-COF in pure acetonitrile versus mixed acetonitrile/water solutions.

Figure S31. *In situ* DRIFTS on 3DOM-COF with BA under dark and irradiation conditions.

Figure S32. *In situ* DRIFTS on ZCS with BA under dark and irradiation conditions.

Theoretical calculation

Figure S33. The supercells and geometries used for the computational study. The parts allowed to optimize are shown.

Figure S34. Geometrical structures of the different intermediates along the reaction path, on the ZCS substrate.

Figure S35. Geometrical structures of the different intermediates along the reaction path, on the 3DOM-COF substrate.

Figure S36. Geometrical structures of the different intermediates along the reaction path, on the ZCS/3DOM-COF substrate.

Figure S37. Partial density of states (PDOS) of the three different substrates for the potential determining step intermediate (*PhCH₂NH).

Charge separation efficiency analysis

Figure S38. Transient photocurrent response of different samples.

Note: As shown in Figure S38, compared to the B-COF with only micropores, the 3DOM-COF with a 3DOM structure demonstrates faster separation of photogenerated charge carriers. The transient photocurrent measurements also indicate that the ZCS/3DOM-COF catalyst exhibits the highest photocurrent density, suggesting the fastest separation of photogenerated charge carriers in the ZCS/3DOM-COF catalyst.

Figure S39. EIS Nyquist plots of different samples.

Note: Figure S39 depicts the EIS of different samples. In comparison to 3DOM-COF and ZCS, ZCS/3DOM-COF exhibits smaller arc radii, indicating that the S-scheme heterojunction can facilitate the transfer of photogenerated charge carriers.

Compared to the ZCS/B-COF, the ZCS/3DOM-COF demonstrates smaller arc radii, indicating the 3DOM-structure favors to enhance the interface carrier transfer in S-scheme heterojunction.

Figure S40. SPV spectra of 3DOM-COF, ZCS and ZCS/3DOM-COF, respectively.

Note: The charge separation efficiency was analyzed through steady-state surface photovoltage (SPV) measurements, confirming that ZCS/3DOM-COF exhibits enhanced charge separation and transport properties under illumination, supporting its excellent photocatalytic activity.

Figure S41. PL spectroscopy of 3DOM-COF, ZCS and ZCS/3DOM-COF, respectively.

Note: As shown in Figure S41, the steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra indicate that the recombination in ZCS/3DOM-COF is greatly suppressed compared to the 3DOM-COF and ZCS, suggesting the fast carrier separation in the ZCS/3DOM-COF.

Figure S42. TR-PL spectroscopy of 3DOM-COF, ZCS and ZCS/3DOM-COF, respectively.

Note: As depicted in Figure S42, the time-resolved photoluminescence (TR-PL) spectra show that the average decay lifetime of ZCS/3DOM-COF sample (1.274 ns) is larger compared to 3DOM-COF (1.127 ns) and ZCS (0.888 ns), indicating longer carrier lifetimes in ZCS/3DOM-COF sample for catalytic reaction.

Figure S43. 2D pseudo-color fs-TAS of (a) 3DOM-COF and (b) B-COF. Extracted decay kinetics of (c) 3DOM-COF and (d) B-COF probed at 450 nm.

Note: The 2D pseudo-color fs-TAS spectra of 3DOM-COF and B-COF show broad negative absorption bands in pure water (Figures S43a, b). The carrier dynamics of photoexcited carriers were fitted using a biexponential decay function at 450 nm. The time-fitting parameters τ_1 and τ_3 correspond to charge diffusion on the lattice and the recombination of electrons with trapped holes. As shown in Figure S43c, d, the hole diffusion lifetime of 3DOM-COF on the lattice is relatively shorter (1.15 ps) compared to B-COF, indicating the faster carrier separation.

Geometry and boundary conditions of mass Transfer behavior

Figure S44. The scheme of geometry and boundary conditions for B-COF and 3DOM-COF.

Figure S45: SEM images of (a) Tp-Bpy COF and (b) Tp-Pa COF.

Note: We attempted to extend this method to other COFs such as Tp-Bpy and Tp-Pa. Due to the COF formation proceeds too rapidly. Fast polycondensation leads to premature bulk nucleation in solution, which prevents the framework from forming within the template structure. This mismatch between the nucleation/growth rate and template degradation hinders the generation of ordered macroporosity.

Table: Key porosity parameters, article on activity comparison, boundary conditions and parameters used in simulations, and fs-TA analysis

Table S1. Key porosity parameters of the 3DOM-COF, B-COF, ZCS/3DOM-COF and ZCS/B-COF.

Samples	BET (m ² g ⁻¹)	<i>D</i> _{meso} (nm)	<i>D</i> _{micro} (nm)	<i>V</i> _{total} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
B-COF	720.8	-	1.4	0.7
3DOM-COF	635.2	24.2	1.4	0.9
ZCS/B-COF	668.1		1.4	0.5
ZCS/3DOM-COF	178.1	9.5	1.4	0.2

Note: Calculated from N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms by the BET method; the average diameters of mesopores and micropores are determined by the BJH and NLDFT methods, respectively.

Table S2. Comparison of the performance of H₂ generation and BA oxidation of the reports.

Catalysis	light source	substrate	Efficiency (mmol g ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹)	Ref.
ZCS/ B-COFs	80 W LED λ = 420 nm	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 11.6 NBI: 9.3	This work
ZCS/3DOM- COFs	80 W LED λ = 420 nm	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 17.8 NBI: 15.1	This work
NZCS	300 W Xe lamp	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 4.55 NBI: 3.35	[8]
TFPT-COF/Pt	300 W Xe lamp λ > 420 nm	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ O ₂ : 0.78 NBI :0.32	[9]
TCOF-Pt SA3	300 W Xe lamp	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 0.48 NBI: 0.51	[10]
CoP@ZnIn ₂ S ₄	300 W Xe lamp λ>400 nm	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 4.87 NBI: 3.82	[11]
PdSA-ZIS	Visible light	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 10.2 NBI: 11.1	[12]
BaTiO ₃ @ ZnIn ₂ S ₄	300 W Xe lamp	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 8.04 NBI: 5.59	[13]
Pt@UiO-66- NH ₂ @ZnIn ₂ S ₄	300 W Xe lamp (400–800 nm)	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 0.85 NBI: 4.26	[14]
BP/BWO	300 W Xe lamp	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	C ₂ H ₅ OH: 0.06 NBI: 0.41	[15]
g-C ₃ N ₄ /TiO ₂	300 W Xe lamp (λ > 400 nm)	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 5.1 NBI: 15.5	[16]

PdS/CdS/MoS ₂	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda > 420$ nm	BA (H ₂ O/DMF)	H ₂ : 6.61 NBI: 19.0	[17]
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x /CdS	300 W Xe lamp	BA (H ₂ O/DMF)	H ₂ : 0.22 NBI: 0.16	[18]
CuS/TiO ₂	UV-vis light (320–780 nm)	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 0.71 NBI: 0.88	[19]
Pd-PCN-222/CdS	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda \geq 400$ nm)	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O)	H ₂ : 5.07 NBI: 3.72	[20]
JUC-675	300 W xenon lamp	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O) O ₂	H ₂ O ₂ : 22.8 NBI: 19.2	[21]
BTT-Bpy-COF	5 W*4 LED $\lambda = 465$ nm	BA (CH ₃ CN) O ₂	NBI: 16.7	[22]
MoS ₂ /FP-BTA	sunlight	BA (CH ₃ CN) O ₂	HCOOH: 24.3 NBI: 15.3	[23]
Ni-P COF	15 W white LED light	BA (CH ₃ CN) O ₂	NBI: 12.4	[24]
TFA-TTA-COF	30 W LED $\lambda = 454$ nm	BA (CH ₃ CN/H ₂ O) O ₂	NBI: 2.0	[25]
TpDTz-COF	3 W*4 LED $\lambda = 460$ nm	BA (CH ₃ CN) O ₂	NBI: 36.9	[26]
aza-COF	30 W LED $\lambda = 360$ nm	BA (CH ₃ CN) O ₂	NBI: 0.7	[27]
W ₁₈ O ₄₉ @TpPa-H-0.1	80 W LED	BA (CH ₃ CN)	NBI: 25.0	[28]

$\lambda = 420 \text{ nm}$

O₂

BA: Benzylamine. NBI: Benzenemethanamine. DMF: *N,N*-Dimethylformamide.

AN: Acetonitrile.

Table S3. The fs-TAS analysis of ZCS/B-COF, ZCS/3DOM-COF, and ZCS/3DOM-COF-BA at 450&470&530 nm within 1000 ps.

Sample	Probe (nm)	T ₁ (ps)	T ₂ (ps)	T ₃ (ps)
ZCS/B-COF in H ₂ O solution	450	2.16±0.21(38%)	19.38±2.05(31%)	184.73±13.36(31%)
	470	2.29±0.23(46%)	20.15±2.58(27%)	222.13±22.59(27%)
	530	1.25±0.10(64%)	19.70±3.22(20%)	185.22±33.48(16%)
ZCS/3DOM-COF in H ₂ O solution	450	0.95±0.13(79%)	6.31±1.19(11%)	23.01±11.74(10%)
	470	1.52±0.21(49%)	16.62±2.31(27%)	154.46±24.38(24%)
	530	1.89±0.61(48%)	16.37±2.25(24%)	163.53±38.42(28%)
ZCS/3DOM-COF in BA/H ₂ O solution	450	0.55±0.15(75%)	3.07±0.53(14%)	12.53±4.67(11%)
	470	0.41±0.11(69%)	7.01±0.94(17%)	58.88±5.53(14%)
	530	2.19±0.57(34%)	25.73±3.94(50%)	247.02±99.97(16%)

Table S4. Boundary conditions and parameters used in simulations.^[28]

Boundary conditions	descriptions
Boundary 1, 2	Concentration; $C=C_0$
Boundary 3, 4	Periodic Condition $C_{src} = C_{dst}$; $-n_{src} \cdot N_{src} = n_{dst} \cdot N_{dst}$
Physical parameters	Value
BA initial concentration	$C_0=171 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
Diffusion coefficient of BA	$1\cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
Density of COF	$952.6 \text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
Density of BA solution	$807 \text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
Hole size of 3DOM-COF	340 nm

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